

Biomass Study of Mangroves in Indian Sundarbans: A Case Study from Satjelia Island

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Abstract

A study was conducted during January 2017 on the biomass of dominant mangrove species in Satjelia Island, located in the central Indian Sundarbans. Eight species of true mangroves were documented in the selected plots. The mean order of abundance of these species was *Avicennia alba* (23.33%) > *Avicennia marina* (20.00%) > *Excoecaria agallocha* (16.66%) > *Sonneratia apetala* (13.33%) = *Avicennia officinalis* (13.33%) > *Acanthus ilicifolius* (6.66%) > *Aegiceros corniculatum* (3.33%) = *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza* (3.33%). The above ground stem biomass of the dominant mangrove trees were 19.79 t ha⁻¹, 5.83 t ha⁻¹, 20.22 t ha⁻¹, 21.14 t ha⁻¹, and 6.70 t ha⁻¹ for *Sonneratia apetala*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Avicennia alba*, *Avicennia marina* and *Avicennia officinalis* respectively.

Keywords: Mangroves, Indian Sundarbans, Satjelia Island, relative abundance, above ground stem biomass.

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1. Introduction

The term mangrove has originated from the Portuguese word ‘*Mangue*’, which means the community and the English word ‘*Grove*’, which means trees or bushes. According to researchers [1], the term “mangrove” has been inconsistent and confusing in the past. Mangroves are basically the evergreen sclerophyllous, broad-leaved trees with aerial root like pnuematophore or stilt root and viviparous germinated seedlings [2]. They grow along protected sedimentary shores specially in tidal lagoons, embayments and estuaries [3]. They also can grow far inland, but never isolated from the sea. These emergent, evergreen canopies are found along the sedimentary shores of both tropical and sub-tropical regions in association with intertidal flora and fauna commonly known as mangrove ecosystem and the community of these mangroves (including micro and macro-organisms) was termed by Macnae [3] as Mangal. The mangal is therefore a broad domain encompassing the entire biotic community comprising of individual plant species, associated microbes (like bacteria and fungi), and animals. The mangal and its associated abiotic factors constitute the mangrove ecosystem, which is a unique ecosystem of the globe.

Earlier study [4] expressed the word ‘mangrove’ of coastal ecosystem in a holistic manner, including its common habitat or inhabiting species. About 60 – 75% of tropical coastline is fringed with mangroves [5]. According to scientist mangroves as

“.... A tree, shrub, palm and ground fern, generally exceeding one half meter in height and which normally grows above mean sea level in the intertidal zone of marine coastal environments or estuarine margins....” [6].

This definition is acceptable except that ground ferns should be considered as mangrove associates rather than true mangroves.

Mangroves are circumtropical in distribution. This forest community occupies approximately 75% of the total tropical coastline. Northern extension of this coastline occurs in Japan (31⁰22’N) and Bermuda (32⁰20’N), whereas, southern extensions are in New Zealand (38⁰03’S), Australia (38⁰45’S) and on the east coast of South Africa (32⁰59’S). Globally, mangroves are distributed in 112 countries and

territories. It is interesting to note that mangrove plants are not native to the Hawaiian Islands - 6 species have been introduced there since the year 1900. The total global coverage of mangroves has been variously estimated as 14 - 15 million hectares [7], 10 million hectares [8] and 24 million hectares [9]. The major mangrove rich countries in Indian Ocean region are listed in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1: List of mangrove rich countries in Indian Ocean region

Country	Mangrove Area*
Indonesia	42,500
Myanmar	6,950
Malaysia	6,410
India	4,871
NW Australia	4,513
Bangladesh	4,500
Madagascar	4,200
Mozambique	4,000
Pakistan	2,600
Thailand	1,900

*(in Km²)

Figure 1. Rich countries in mangrove in Indian Ocean region (Adapted) [10]

Biomass study of mangrove trees (irrespective of species) is extremely important and it is the sum of the biomass of its roots, pneumatophores, trunk, branches, leaves, and reproductive organs like flowers and fruits. Detailed estimations of biomass of mangrove species are extremely important in the present *era* due to following reasons:

- i. Biomass estimation provides direct picture of commercial viability of mangrove species in terms of timber, wood, honey, wax etc.
- ii. Biomass of mangroves provides information on their primary production capacity.
- iii. The detritus contributed by the mangrove vegetation not only nourishes the adjacent water bodies and promotes fisheries, but also act as the foundation of detritus food chain in the inter-tidal zone. The detritus are nothing but contributory components of leaves, branches, fruits, and flowers of mangroves.

In the present dissertation only the stem biomasses of 5 dominant mangrove species were estimated in the mangrove patch at Annpur village in Satjelia Island of central Indian Sundarbans.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 Selection of the sampling stations

The study site is located in the central part of Indian Sundarbans, at the apex of Bay of Bengal and locally the place is known as Annpur. Samplings were carried out during low tide period from 10th to 25th January, 2017 in the intertidal mudflats of Annpur. The plants in this site grew naturally since 1988, almost 30 years old. Plot size of 10 m × 10 m was selected for the study and the average readings were documented from 5 such plots (centre coordinates 22°11'52"N latitude and 88°50'43"E longitude). The mean relative abundance of each species was evaluated for the order of dominance of mangrove species at the study site.

The above ground biomass of individual trees in each plot was estimated as per the standard procedure stated here and the average values of 15 plots were finally converted into biomass of five dominant mangrove species (in tonnes) per hectare in the study area.

2.2 Above ground stem biomass estimation

The above ground (stem) biomass for each species in every plot was estimated using non-destructive method in which the diameter at the breast height (DBH) was measured with a caliper and height with common trigonometrical formula after estimating the angle between the eye and the highest part of the stem (Figure 2). Form factor was determined with using the standard equation [11]. Specific gravity (G) was estimated taking the stem cores, which was further converted into stem biomass (B_s) as per the expression $B_s = GV$. The expression for V is $FH\pi R^2$, where F is the form factor, R is the radius of the tree derived from its DBH and H is the height of the target tree.

Figure 2. A simple device to measure the tree height

3. Result and Discussion

The biomass and productivity of mangrove forests have been studied mainly in terms of wood production, forest conservation, and ecosystem management [12-17]. The contemporary understanding of the global warming phenomenon, however, has generated interest in the carbon-stocking ability of mangroves. The carbon sequestration in this unique producer community is a function of biomass production capacity, which in turn depends upon interaction between edaphic, climate, and topographic factors of an area. Hence, results obtained at one place

may not be applicable to another. Therefore region based potential of different land types needs to be worked out. In the present study, the results obtained have been compared with other regions of the world to evaluate the role of Indian Sundarbans mangrove as carbon sink on the background of changing scenario of the climate.

3.1 Relative abundance

Eight species of true mangroves were documented in the selected plots. The mean order of abundance of these species was *Avicennia alba* (23.33%) > *Avicennia marina* (20.00%) > *Excoecaria agallocha* (16.66%) > *Sonneratia apetala* (13.33%) = *Avicennia officinalis* (13.33%) > *Acanthus ilicifolius* (6.66%) > *Aegiceros corniculatum* (3.33%) = *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza* (3.33%) (Table 2). Few mangrove associate floral species (like *Porteresia coarctata*, *Suaeda* sp. etc.) were also documented in the plots, but on the basis of relative abundance of the true mangrove species, only five dominant species namely, *Avicennia alba*, *Avicennia marina*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Sonneratia apetala*, and *Avicennia officinalis* were considered for carbon stock estimation in their respective above ground biomass.

Table 2: Relative abundance of mangrove species (mean of 15 plots) in the study area

Species	No.*	RA**
<i>Sonneratia apetala</i>	4	13.33
<i>Excoecaria agallocha</i>	5	16.66
<i>Avicennia alba</i>	7	23.33
<i>Avicennia marina</i>	6	20.00
<i>Avicennia officinalis</i>	4	13.33
<i>Acanthus ilicifolius</i>	2	6.66
<i>Aegiceros corniculatum</i>	1	3.33
<i>Bruguiera gymnorrhiza</i>	1	3.33

*No. of species/100 m²; **Relative abundance (%)

3.2 Above ground stem biomass

The above ground stem biomass of the dominant mangrove trees were 19.79 t ha⁻¹, 5.83 t ha⁻¹, 20.22 t ha⁻¹, 21.14 t ha⁻¹, and 6.70 t ha⁻¹ for *Sonneratia apetala*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Avicennia alba*, *Avicennia marina*, and *Avicennia officinalis* respectively (Table 3). These values are comparatively lesser to the data of earlier study [18] in a secondary mangrove (*Ceriops tagal*) forest at Southern Thailand. It was documented that the stem biomass formed 62.49%, 59.92%, 56.81%, 60.61% and 59.50% of the total above ground biomass of *Sonneratia apetala*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Avicennia alba*, *Avicennia marina*, and *Avicennia officinalis* respectively.

Table 3: Above ground biomass (t/ha) of five dominant mangrove species in the intertidal mudflats of Annpur.

Part	A	B	C	D	E
Stem	19.79	5.83	20.22	21.14	6.70

A = *Sonneratia apetala*, B = *Excoecaria agallocha*, C = *Avicennia alba*, D = *Avicennia marina*, E = *Avicennia officinalis*.

4. Conclusion

Mangrove forests, mostly concentrated at the land-sea interface and estuarine delta naturally sequester carbon dioxide during photosynthesis. Over time carbon accumulates in the trees, forest-floor (in litter) and especially soil. Approximately 35% - 45% of the dry above ground biomass of trees is made up of carbon (as revealed from direct %C analysis through CHN analyzer); thus as long as the tree is growing and accumulating biomass, it is accumulating carbon. Here we have provided a comprehensive synthesis of the available data on mangrove stem biomass in a forest patch of central Indian Sundarbans of 30 years old. More standardization is needed to reach the accuracy in estimation. The present study is important because biomass estimation provides direct picture of commercial viability of mangrove species in terms of timber, wood, honey, wax etc. Moreover biomass of mangroves provides information on their primary production capacity and carbon storing capacity.

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